

TN on Quality Assessment for PlanetScope (DOVE)

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The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

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0.2	12/09/2019	Second draft after ESA review
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0.4	23/10/2019	Fourth draft after NPL review
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1.0	17/01/2020	Updated following RIDs received from ESA 11/12/2019
1.1	01/04/2020	Updated following editorial comments received from ESA 25/03/2020
1.2	26/04/2020	Updated with links to online reference documents, and modification to Maturity Matrix Table 3-1
1.3	25/11/2020	Updated version addressing all ESA and Planet feedback received June 2020

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
2. INTRODUCTION.....	6
2.1 Reference Documents	6
2.2 Glossary	9
3. EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT	11
3.1 EDAP Maturity Matrix.....	11
3.2 Summary of Quality Assessment.....	12
4. DETAILED EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT	14
4.1 Product Information	14
4.2 Product Generation	15
4.3 Ancillary Information.....	16
4.4 Uncertainty Characterisation.....	16
4.5 Validation.....	17
5. DETAILED PLANETSCOPE QUALITY ASSESSMENT	18
5.1 Goals.....	18
5.2 Product documentation evaluation.....	18
5.3 Product format evaluation	21
5.4 Image quality.....	26
5.4.1 Image quality measures	27
5.4.2 Visual inspection.....	29
5.4.3 Rating scale	31
5.5 Geometric Calibration / Validation.....	33
5.5.1 Activity Description Sheet.....	33
5.5.2 Tools	33
5.5.3 Regions of interest.....	33
5.5.4 PlanetScope Data.....	34
5.5.5 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy.....	35
5.5.5.1 Methods	35
5.5.5.2 Results	35
5.5.6 Multi-temporal Geolocation Accuracy.....	40
5.5.6.1 Methods	40
5.5.6.2 Results	40
5.5.7 Inter-band Registration Accuracy	59
5.5.7.1 Methods	59
5.5.7.2 Results	60
5.6 Radiometric Calibration / Validation: Cross calibration between PlanetScope AND SENTINEL-2 MSI / LANDSAT 8 OLI data over PICS	62
5.6.1 Activity Description Sheet.....	62
5.6.2 Introduction	62
5.6.3 Methods and Tools	63
5.6.3.1 Methods	63
5.6.3.2 Tools	63
5.6.4 Region of interest.....	63
5.6.4.1 Planet Data	64
5.6.4.2 Landsat Data.....	64
5.6.4.3 Sentinel-2 Data	64
5.6.5 Prediction Model Estimation	65
5.6.6 Cross calibration Statistics	68
5.7 Radiometric Calibration / Validation: Absolute calibration of PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 MSI by using RadCalNet	71
5.7.1 Activity Description Sheet.....	71
5.7.2 Introduction	71
5.7.3 Methods and Tools	71
5.7.3.1 Methods	71
5.7.3.2 Tools	72

5.7.4	Dataset	73
5.7.4.1	Region of interest.....	73
5.7.4.2	Planet Data	73
5.7.4.3	Sentinel-2 Data	73
5.7.4.4	Modis Data.....	73
5.7.5	Calibration results	73
6.	CONCLUSIONS.....	76
6.1	Geometric calibration	76
6.2	Radiometric assessment.....	76
APPENDIX A	PLANETSCOPE (DOVE) MISSION.....	78
APPENDIX B	LIST OF PLANETSCOPE PRODUCTS USED	80

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary purpose of the activity performed with PlanetScope data is to ensure that the product conforms to the declared quality.

The assessment focused on the product details provided, the geolocation accuracies and the radiometric calibration. All products were acquired from the PlanetScope-2 sensors belonging to the Flocks-3p and Flocks-2k satellites launched 15/02/2017 and 14/07/2018, respectively. All the products considered were processed with the version 4.1.4 of the CMO Patch Processor.

The report is divided in two sections: in the first section (Section 4) the results are summarised following the EDAP guidelines document [RD-1]. The subsequent section (Section 5) contains the detailed assessment performed and summarised in the first section.

The analysis of the product information resulted in intermediate values, with the possibility of improvements. The products conform to international standards; the archive is easily accessible; however, it requires a subscription to be able to check the products. The user documentation refers to the product specification only (see more details in Section 5.2).

The sensor calibration pre- and post-flight has been presented in different events, and it was also assessed independently by third parties (e.g. USGS contractors) however, given the number of satellites involved in the constellation the results are difficult to interpret.

The image quality, geometric and radiometric activities performed demonstrate that differences between data are important, and strongly depend on the selected satellite.

The constellation is definitively heterogeneous (see section 5.5.4). The technology used for PlanetScope is very simple and these assessments confirm the trade-off made by Planet.

In terms of product design, the format is very simple with the minimum level of metadata. The quality assurance data are available as part of the metadata as well as in the form of a binary mask. The quality mask is in the process of being improved, however several inconsistencies exist, as shown in the report.

The visual inspection / image quality activity confirms that the image is often contaminated by motion blur, the spatial resolution is dramatically degraded, and ground features that should be identified at 3.125 m resolution are missed.

The validation of radiometric calibration demonstrates with two different approaches that the absolute calibration accuracy of Planetscope is degraded in all bands.

The validation of the geometric calibration confirms that the L1C product geolocation accuracy is in agreement with the Planet specification (10.0 m Root Mean Square Error (**RMSE**)). However, it is important to highlight that important distortions exist in the internal imagery, mainly caused by the fact that the sensor is a CCD Array.

2. INTRODUCTION

This document is the Technical Note on Quality Assessment report for the PlanetScope (DOVE) mission.

The quality assessment provides a series of checks on the product format and metadata; checks on the geometric and radiometric validation were performed on a limited number of products.

Please note that it is possible that these products were updated since the analysis described in this document.

The quality assessment performed here is in line with the assessment guidelines provided in the EARTHNET Data Assessment Pilot (**EDAP**) project RD-1.

2.1 Reference Documents

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this Technical Note. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP.REP.001 Quality Assessment Guidelines, 1.2 19 July 2019

- RD-2. Planet Imagery Product Specifications
<https://assets.planet.com/docs/combined-imagery-product-spec-final-may-2019.pdf>

- RD-3. Saunier, Sébastien & Goryl, Philippe & Chander, Gyanesh & Santer, Richard & Bouvet, Marc & Collet, Bernard & Mambimba, Aboubakar & Kocaman, Sultan. (2010). Radiometric, geometric, and image quality assessment of ALOS AVNIR-2 and PRISM sensors. IEEE T. Geoscience and Remote Sensing. 48. 10.1109/TGRS.2010.2048714.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262804365_Radiometric_geometric_and_image_quality_assessment_of_ALOS_AVNIR-2_and_PRISM_sensors

- RD-4. Pablo d'Angelo, Evaluation Of Skybox Video And Still Image Products, ISPRS November 2014
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280744579_Evaluation_of_Skybox_Video_and_Still_Image_products

- RD-5. N. Wilson, Planet, "Absolute Radiometric Calibration of the Planet DOVE Satellites", JACIE 2017

- RD-6. D. Varlyguin, GDA Corp., "Assessment of the Radiometric Calibration of PlanetScope 2 DOVE Imagery"

- RD-7. H. Cosnefroy, M. Leroy, X. Briottet, Selection and characterization of Saharan and Arabian desert sites for the calibration of optical satellite sensors, *Remote Sensing of Environ.*, Vol. 58, N°1, pp 101-114, 1996
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0034425795002111?via%3Dihub>
- RD-8. T. Tadono, M. Shimada, H. Murakami, J. Takaku "Calibration of PRISM and AVNIR-2 Onboard ALOS "Daichi"," *Geoscience and Remote Sensing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol.47, no.12, pp.4042,4050, Dec. 2009 doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2009.2025270 <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5208235>
- RD-9. M. Bouvet, "Intercomparison of multispectral imagers over natural targets," in *Proc. IGARSS, Barcelona, Spain, 2007*
<https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2007.4423390>
- RD-10. H. Murakami, T. Tadono, H. Imai, J. Nieke, and M. Shimada, "Improvement of AVNIR-2 Radiometric Calibration by Comparison of Cross-Calibration and Onboard Lamp Calibration," *IEEE Trans. Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 47, no. 12, pp. 4051–4059, Dec. 2009
<https://www.researchgate.net/deref/http%3A%2F%2Fdx.doi.org%2F10.1109%2FTGRS.2009.2018118>
- RD-11. G. Chander, D. Meyer, and D. L. Helder, "Cross-calibration of the Landsat 7 ETM+ and EO ALI sensor," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 42, no. 12, pp. 2821–2831, Dec. 2004
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1369378>
- RD-12. K. J. Thome, "In-flight intersensor radiometric calibration using vicarious approaches," *Post-Launch Calibration of Satellite Sensors*, Edited by S. A. Morain and A. M. Budge, Balkema Publishers, Philadelphia, pp. 93-102, 2004
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260182735_Inflight_Intersensor_Radiometric_Calibration_using_the_Reflectance-Based_Method_for_Landsat-Type_Sensors
- RD-13. JACIE 2017 presentation, <https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/Paul-Bresnahan-1.pdf> :
- RD-14. CEOS, RadCalNet Quick Start Guide. July 2018
https://www.radcalnet.org/resources/RadCalNetQuickstartGuide_20180702.pdf
- RD-15. Cournet M., Giros A., Dumas L., Delvit J. M., Greslou D., Languille F., Michel J. "2D Sub-Pixel Disparity Measurement Using QPEC/Medicis,"

International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial
Information Sciences, 41 (2016).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303800733_2D_Sub-Pixel_Disparity_Measurement_Using_QPEC_Medicis

- RD-16. Gruen, A., & Kocaman, S. (2008). *Optical Sensors High Resolution: Geometry Validation Methodology* (Doctoral dissertation, 2008, Institute of Geodesy and Photogrammetry).
http://calvalportal.ceos.org/c/document_library/get_file?uuid=0e60ed79-2065-4dab-b1db-d1d06fbb1ae1&groupId=10136
- RD-17. M. Blanc. (2008). Image quality Needs, Calibration / Validation Test site project – PM1 (23/05/2008) – ESA Project WP 224
- RD-18. J. Schott “Remote Sensing The image chain approach” Second Edition, Oxford University Press 2007,
- RD-19. Copernicus data Quality Control - Technical Note, PlanetScope Technical Document Review, CDS-TPZ-03-000077-TR, 19/09/2017
https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/documents/12833/14545/D-067_CQC_T7_TN_005_v4.pdf
- RD-20. Jérémy Anger and AI, “Assessing the sharpness of satellite images: study of the PlanetScope constellation” 19/04/2019 arXiv:1904.09159.
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1904.09159.pdf>
- RD-21. MTF Determination from PlanetScope data – PlanetScope MTF Report - Technical Note, AIRBUS DS Document, 21/12/2017
- RD-22. F. Viallefont, D. Helder, R. Fraisse, A. Newbury, F. Van Der Bergh, D. Lee and S. Saunier, “Comparison of MTF measurements using the edge method”. *Opt Express*. 2018 Dec 24;26(26):33625-33648. doi: 10.1364/OE.26.033625.
https://www.osapublishing.org/DirectPDFAccess/B52B7E69-D513-7B6C-D19125BD5D60FBED_402992/oe-26-26-33625.pdf?da=1&id=402992&seq=0&mobile=no
- RD-23. R. D. Fiete, “Image quality and $[\lambda]FN/p$ for remote sensing systems”, *Optical Engineering*, 38(7), (1999). <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.602169>
- RD-24. Planet L1 Data Quality Report Q2 2019 – Status of calibration and Data Quality for the PlanetScope Constellation.

2.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document
B	Blue
BRDF	Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CE	Circular Error
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellite
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DN	Digital Number
EDAP	EARTHNET Data Assessment Pilot
ESF	Edge Spread Function
G	Green
GCPs	Ground Control Points
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GIFOV	Ground Instantaneous Field of View
GRD	Ground Resolved Distance
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
HR	High Resolution
ISS	International Space Station
JACIE	Joint Agency Commercial Imagery Evaluation
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MPC	Mission Performance Centre
MSI	Multi Spectral Imager
<i>MTF</i>	<i>Modulation Transfer Function</i>
NIIRS	National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale
NIR	Near Infrared
NPL	National Physical Laboratory
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGR	OpenGIS Simple Feature Reference Implementation
OLI	Operational Land Imager
PDI	Product Data Item
PICS	Pseudo Invariant Calibration Sites
PS0	PlanetScope 0
PS1	PlanetScope 1
<i>PS2</i>	<i>PlanetScope 2</i>
PSF	Point Spread Function
QC	Quality Control
R	Red

RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RSR	Relative Spectral Response
SBAFs	Spectral Band Adjustment Factors
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
TDI	Time Delay Integration
TN	Technical Note
TOA	Top-Of-Atmosphere
UDM	Unusable Data Mask
UDM2	Usable Data Mask
VHR	Very High Resolution
ZNCC	Zero Normalized Cross Correlation

3. EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT

3.1 EDAP Maturity Matrix

The preliminary assessment was performed following the EDAP quality assessment guidelines written by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) [RD-1], with the summary reported and detailed analysis within Section 4. It is considered as a ‘preliminary assessment’ as it was prepared using a limited number of products over specific calibration sites.

Table 3-1: PlanetScope DOVE Quality Maturity Matrix

Product Information	Product Generation	Ancillary Information	Uncertainty Characterisation	Validation
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Pre-Flight	Product Flags	Uncertainty Characterisation Method	Reference Data Representativeness
Availability & Accessibility	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Post-Launch	Additional Information	Uncertainty Sources Included	Reference Data Quality
Product Format	Additional Processing		Uncertainty Values Provided	Validation Method
User Documentation			Geolocation Uncertainty	Validation Results
Metrological Traceability Documentation				

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Intermediate
Good
Excellent

 Information not public

3.2 Summary of Quality Assessment

Assessment of the product details, geolocation uncertainties and radiometric calibration were performed using the PlanetScope (DOVE) constellation [APPENDIX A] products listed in APPENDIX B.

Table 3-2 Executive Summary

Assessment	Results
Product details	The product format is detailed and well structured, the metadata information strongly relies on the various Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards.
Visual assessment	Visual inspection highlighted good visual quality of the data. However, it was reported some degree of inconsistencies between the data quality observed by different satellites.
Geometric accuracy	<p>The Absolute geometric error has been assessed.</p> <p>Results are fully in agreement with the product accuracy specifications (10.0 m RMSE).</p> <p>For Piedmont and La Crau, the CE@90 is high compared to RMSE. This is due to internal image distortions.</p> <p>Stability during a long-term period should be analysed more carefully.</p> <p>The multi-temporal geometric accuracy was also tested.</p> <p>The geometry is compared by using dense matching techniques (Zero Normalized Cross Correlation (ZNCC) algorithms). Post processing is applied for selecting points and performing accuracy analysis.</p> <p>The variation of the geometry in the “along track” might be due to attitude errors that are badly modelled / compensated.</p> <p>The accuracy of the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) used for ortho processing might be responsible of some error seen in the line displacement images.</p> <p>Finally, the geometric registration between image bands was compared, also by using intensity based matching techniques.</p> <p>The inter-band registration accuracy is within expectations for Blue (B), Green (G), Red (R) image bands.</p> <p>There are however strong deviations for the Near Infrared (NIR), B band pair.</p> <p>The error budget of the method, related to the measurement accuracy, is generally good, and might be up to 0.25 pixels in some cases.</p>

Assessment	Results
<p>Radiometric accuracy</p>	<p>The inter-comparison of PlanetScope measured radiance with standard missions such as Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Sentinel 2 Multi Spectral Imager (MSI) highlighted differences especially in the B and NIR band. The analysis was performed without adjusting for the different Relative Spectral Response (RSR).</p> <p>At the time of this analysis, the DOVE RSR was not publicly available but was provided directly by Planet to perform absolute radiometric calibration over the RadCalNet site of LaCrau. They are now publicly available here: https://support.planet.com/hc/en-us/articles/360014290293-Do-you-provide-Relative-Spectral-Response-Curves-RSRs-for-your-satellites-</p> <p>The inter-calibration results of PlanetScope obtained over Pseudo Invariant Calibration Sites (PICS) are confirmed with RadCalNet methods, showing a degraded radiometric calibration accuracy.</p>

4. DETAILED EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT

4.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Product Name	<i>PlanetScope OrthoTiles Analytic</i>
Sensor Name	<i>PlanetScope – PlanetScope 2 (PS2) (Flock-3p, Flock-2k)</i>
Sensor Type	<i>Optical MultiSpectral (VNIR)</i>
Product Version Number	<i>Planet Standard product version 1.0 CMO Patch Processor v 4.1.4</i>
Product ID	<i><CatalogueID>_<TileID>_<AcquisitionDate>_<SatelliteID> Example: 2037910_3159122_2019-01-19_1010 Full list in APPENDIX B</i>
Processing level of product	<i>Level 1</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Radiance / Top of Atmosphere Reflectance</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>W sr⁻¹ m⁻² μm⁻¹ / Adimensional</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>PlanetScope constellation Geometric error 10 m RMSE. Unavailable for each product</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>3.125 m (resampled from native ~4.0 m)</i>
Spatial Coverage	<i>25 km x 25 km Tiles</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>Daily global land acquisitions provided by +130 satellite constellation. Temporal revisit time of a single PlanetScope satellite not provided</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>Variable</i>
Point of Contact	www.planet.com
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>none</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>20160101 - Inc - Single User https://assets.planet.com/docs/20160101_Inc_SingleUser.txt</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Available under license</i>
Product Abstract	<i>See APPENDIX A full product description available at: https://assets.planet.com/docs/combined-imagery-product-spec-final-may-2019.pdf</i>

Availability & Accessibility	
Compliant with FAIR principles	Yes
Data Management Plan	<i>Not available to users</i>
Availability Status	<i>Available for download previous commercial license</i>

Product Format

Product File Format	Data encoding is standard GeoTiff with GeoJSON metadata file and XML metadata file
Metadata Conventions	<pre> xsi:schemaLocation="http://schemas.planet.com/ps/v1/planet_product_metadata_geocorrected_level http://schemas.planet.com/ps/v1/planet_product_metadata_geocorrected_level.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xmlns:opt="http://earth.esa.int/opt" xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml" xmlns:eop="http://earth.esa.int/eop" version="1.2.1" planet_standard_product_version="1.0" </pre>
Analysis Ready Data?	No – geometric information missing from metadata, spectral information missing from metadata

User Documentation		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	Product specification document available online (last accessed 10/06/2019): https://assets.planet.com/docs/combined-imagery-product-spec-final-may-2019.pdf Document updated regularly	Partially – user cases and validation missing.
ATBD	Not available to users	

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Document Reference	Processing chain diagram present in the Product Specification document however no information is present regarding the Traceability chain or the uncertainty tree diagram.
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	Not available to users

4.2 Product Generation

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Pre-Flight	
Summary	Public presentation at JACIE workshop: The presented pre-flight calibration consists of calculation of the Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) Flat field noise and the RSR estimated over a few percent of the total number of DOVE satellites.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/apps/sites/default/files/jacie/JACIE-Presentation-Pre-launch-Calibration-of-the-Planet-Labs-PlanetScope-Constellation-1.pdf

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Post-Launch	
Summary	In orbit calibration maintained using Moon reflectance techniques and cross-comparison with Rapid-Eye, Landsat 8 and in situ RadCalNet data. Sensor calibration was checked and results are reported in section 5.6

References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiometric calibration report (last accessed 10/06/2019) • https://support.planet.com/hc/en-us/article_attachments/360018720794/EXTERNAL-Absolute_Radiometric_Calibration_Planet_DOVE_Flocks_2p_2e.pdf • https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/apps/sites/default/files/jacie/ABrunnforJumpusat-Lunarslides.pdf • https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/apps/sites/default/files/jacie/DVarlyguin-GDA_NGA_ASMTofRadCal%20PlanetScope2-JACIE2017.pdf • https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/apps/sites/default/files/jacie/MinsuKimUSGSSRcomparisonLS08OLivsPlanetOLIACmitigation.pdf
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Additional Processing	
<i>Not assessed, because no additional processing is proposed from the standard catalogue.</i>	
Description	N/A
Reference	N/A

4.3 Ancillary Information

Product Flags	
Product Flag Documentation	<i>Unusable Data Mask band (UDM). New Usable data mask (UDM2) available but not present in products analysed. Specification are found in the Planet product specification document [RD.2].</i>
Comprehensiveness of Flags	<i>Cloud mask, detector failure mask</i>

Additional information	
Ancillary Data Documentation	<i>Not available to users</i>
Comprehensiveness of Data	<i>Relative Spectral Response provided for the EDAP project.</i>
Uncertainty Quantified	N/A

4.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

Uncertainty Characterisation Method	
Summary	<i>Not available to users</i>
Reference	N/A

Uncertainty Sources Included	
Summary	<i>Not available to users</i>
Reference	N/A

Uncertainty Values Provided	
Summary	<i>Not available to users</i>

Reference	N/A
Analysis Ready Data?	N/A

Geolocation Uncertainty	
Summary	<i>Presentations available at JACIE workshops from US government contractors.</i>
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://calval.cr.usgs.gov/apps/sites/default/files/jacie/PublicReleaseCase17-582_PlanetFeedContractGeolocAndBandCoreg_09JUN2017.pdf

4.5 Validation

Validation Activity	
Independently Assessed?	<i>Yes – JACIE presentations have radiometric and geometric calibration activities performed by US government contractors and Planet internal works.</i>
<i>Reference Data Representativeness</i>	
Summary	<i>Geolocation and radiometric accuracy were tested on limited number of locations.</i>
Reference	<i>This report</i>
<i>Reference Data Quality & Suitability</i>	
Summary	<i>Sentinel-2A and Landsat-8 are typically missions used as reference as their accuracy is high and well documented</i>
Reference	https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/685211/Sentinel-2_User_Handbook https://www.usgs.gov/land-resources/nli/landsat/landsat-8-data-users-handbook
<i>Validation Method</i>	
Summary	<i>Relative and absolute geolocation and radiometric accuracy</i>
Reference	<i>See sections 4.5, 4.6, 4.7</i>
<i>Validation Results</i>	
Summary	<p><i>The absolute geolocation of the products analysed is within the product specification. The relative geolocation suffers from internal geometry distortions, possibly due to satellite attitude and elevation changes.</i></p> <p><i>The radiometric cross-correlation of DOVE shows differences up to 18% with Sentinel-2 data. The absolute calibration is consistent with these differences.</i></p>
Reference	<i>See sections 4.5, 4.6, 4.7</i>

5. DETAILED PLANETSCOPE QUALITY ASSESSMENT

5.1 Goals

Considering the innovative and often challenging technology associated with Very High Resolution (**VHR**) and High Resolution (**HR**) data, this Technical Note (**TN**) reports the results of the performed quality assessment with respect to geometric, radiometric and image quality aspects, as follows:

- The absolute geolocation accuracy of PlanetScope data.
- The image internal geometry of small satellite data is generally unstable. Internal distortions exist and it is therefore essential to check this quality aspect. The distortions (from “jitter”) are often difficult to model as shown in [RD-4]. To overcome this issue, during the ortho-processing, large quantities of accurate Ground Control Points (**GCPs**) with a correct spatial distribution are required (more GCPs than for a standard mission).
- The multi-temporal geometric registration accuracy is often also unstable for VHR and HR missions. A representative data sample is required across the constellation in order to check multi-temporal geometric registration quality.
- The radiometric calibration consistency and calibration is important for multi temporal analysis. With a PlanetScope constellation of more than 100 satellites, the measured radiance depends on the sensor and changing viewing conditions (sun sensor view angle). Some of these points have been discussed during the Joint Agency Commercial Imagery Evaluation (**JACIE**) Workshops (see [RD-5] and [RD-6]). As shown in those presentations, the calibration methods are not sufficiently detailed and synthetic absolute calibration results are not given or the precision is too high to be considered of a reliable accuracy (when using precision as a confidence indicator).
- For VHR data, mainly dedicated to mapping objects, the capability to identify an object is a major requirement. This capability depends on the image quality of the product. The approach used for small satellites is, in general, to apply processing to the raw data to restore it. In the case of the PlanetScope mission, sensor specific processing includes the de-mosaicking of an image from the Bayer Charge-Coupled Device (**CCD**), and this would also apply to any Time Delay Integration (**TDI**) sensor (notably with Pan sharpening). Unfortunately, this processing introduces artefacts in the image, which are then filtered out, which may result in a final image having a low Signal to Noise Ratio (**SNR**) and a low MTF.
- The quality information available in existing publications was also reviewed, which allows definition of a baseline for comparison of the early assessment results.

5.2 Product documentation evaluation

The PlanetScope imagery full specification document is available online [RD-2]. No Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (**ATBD**) is available. The PlanetScope documentation regards the products specification only. In comparison, the ESA Sentinel-2 documentation is broader and comprehends several aspects of the mission. In this section a comparison is provided of the Planet user guide documentation with respect to the relative Sentinel-2 user guide documentation. Documents and or any information available for Sentinel-2 not listed in this section can be considered not available for Planet products.

Mission overview

Planet provides an initial section with the mission overview including the main satellite and sensor parameters. However, the section indicates each parameter for the entire constellation and does not provide indications on the differences between the different PlanetScope satellites currently in orbit in terms of 1) PlanetScope satellite and sensor

design differences, 2) different quality parameters for each satellite sensor type, and 3) the exact ranges of spatial resolution and frame size (currently just specified as “approximate” in the PlanetScope Mission overview document) (Figure 5-1).

CONSTELLATION OVERVIEW: PLANETSCOPE

Mission Characteristics	International Space Station Orbit	Sun-synchronous Orbit
Orbit Altitude (reference)	400 km (51.6° inclination)	475 km (~98° inclination)
Max/Min Latitude Coverage	±52° (depending on season)	±81.5° (depending on season)
Equator Crossing Time	Variable	9:30 - 11:30 am (local solar time)
Sensor Type	Three-band frame Imager or four-band frame Imager with a split-frame NIR filter	Three-band frame Imager or four-band frame Imager with a split-frame NIR filter
Spectral Bands	Blue: 455 - 515 nm Green: 500 - 590 nm Red: 590 - 670 nm NIR: 780 - 860 nm	Blue: 455 - 515 nm Green: 500 - 590 nm Red: 590 - 670 nm NIR: 780 - 860 nm
Ground Sample Distance (nadir)	3.0 m (approximate)	3.7 m
Frame Size	20 km x 12 km (approximate)	24.6 km x 16.4 km (approximate)
Maximum Image Strip per orbit	8,100 km ²	20,000 km ²
Revisit Time	Variable	Daily at nadir (early 2017)
Image Capture Capacity	Variable	200 million km ² /day

Figure 5-1: PlanetScope Mission overview document table.

The overview section of the Sentinel User guide contains a similar table, with the comparison to heritage missions. The table contains less parameters compared to Planet products. However, all the parameter listed in the PlanetScope mission overview are explained in specific sections in the Sentinel user guide, whereas there are no further details for some of the fields present in the table depicted in Figure 5-2.

Products type

The Planet product description document continues with the different products available. Planet provides the L1A, L3A and L3B PlanetScope products to the users, which are not immediately comparable to Sentinel-2 products due to the acquisition difference between the frame-based detector and the push broom sensor design of PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 sensors respectively. The description of the different product types for PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 data is provided below.

PLANETSCOPE SATELLITE IMAGE PRODUCT PROCESSING LEVELS

Name	Description	Product Level
PlanetScope Basic Scene Product	Scaled Top of Atmosphere Radiance (at sensor) and sensor corrected product. The Basic Scene product is designed for users with advanced image processing and geometric correction capabilities. This product has scene based framing and is not projected to a cartographic projection. Radiometric and sensor corrections applied to the data.	Level 1B
PlanetScope Ortho Scene Product	Orthorectified, scaled Top of Atmosphere Radiance (at sensor) or Surface Reflectance image product suitable for analytic and visual applications. This product has scene based framing and projected to a cartographic projection.	Level 3B
PlanetScope Ortho Tile Product	Radiometric and sensor corrections applied to the data. Imagery is orthorectified and projected to a UTM projection.	Level 3A

Name	High-level description	Production & Distribution	Data Volume
Level-1B	Top-of-atmosphere radiances in sensor geometry	Systematic generation and on-line distribution	27 MB (each 25x23 km ²)
Level-1C	Top-of-atmosphere reflectances in cartographic geometry	Systematic generation and on-line distribution	500 MB (each 100x100 km ²)
Level-2A	Bottom-of-atmosphere reflectances in cartographic geometry (prototype product)	Generation on user side (using Sentinel-2 Toolbox)	600 MB (each 100x100 km ²)

Figure 5-2: Comparison of Planet DOVE (top) and Sentinel-2 (bottom) products available to users.

In the Planet product description document, the basic characteristics of each PlanetScope product type are listed and explained. For Sentinel-2, a separate document for the Product specification is provided which encompasses all the aspects of the product, from product definitions to a full detailed description of each Product Data Item (PDI). The fields present in each PlanetScope product were compared to the Product specification document and they resulted compliant to the specifications.

As for the Sentinel-2 documentation, all the fields present in the PlanetScope product metadata file are listed and explained. The product structure is summarised in a table and each file delivered in a PlanetScope product is summarised and explained.

Notably, Planet introduced a new Usable Data Mask (UDM2) in their products. This additional band has the function of a quality band and gives information regarding clouds, shadows, snow and other field of view obstruction elements (e.g. haze).

Product processing

The product description document provided by Planet continues with a section relative to the processing chain. The section is mainly composed of a table and a graph that summarises the processing steps performed and the differences between the products processing levels. The level of details of that section informs the users about the processing blocks (e.g. radiometric calibration, geometric corrections) expected for each product type but does not reach the completeness of an ATBD, which is distributed for Sentinel-2 products.

Data delivery options

The document concludes explaining the different delivery options available to the users, namely the API and the GUI with the links to their platform.

5.3 Product format evaluation

The consistency and completeness of metadata, the compliancy with standards (ISO, QA4EO etc.) and Mission / Data Provider format specification was checked. The approach focused on the detailed analysis of the product format and comparison with 'gold standard' ESA missions.

For instance, as shown in Figure 5-3, the metadata for the PlanetScope products is stored in a JavaScript Object Notation (**JSON**) file with observation angles given except the viewing azimuth angle. This is not considered critical, since this information exists in a second XML metadata file, present for PlanetScope products.

```

  <_links:
    <_self: "https://api.planet.com/data/v1/item-types/PSOrthoTile/items/2037910_3159121_2019-01-19_1010"
    <assets: "https://api.planet.com/data/v1/item-types/PSOrthoTile/items/2037910_3159121_2019-01-19_1010/assets/"
    <thumbnail: "https://tiles.planet.com/data/v1/item-types/PSOrthoTile/items/2037910_3159121_2019-01-19_1010/thumb"
  >_permissions: [-]
  >geometry:
    >coordinates: [-]
    type: "Polygon"
    id: "2037910_3159121_2019-01-19_1010"
  >properties:
    acquired: "2019-01-19T10:05:36.896044Z"
    anomalous_pixels: 0.1
    black_fill: 0.07
    cloud_cover: 0.096
    columns: 8000
    epsg_code: 32631
    grid_cell: "3159121"
    ground_control: true
    gsd: 3.9
    item_type: "PSOrthoTile"
    origin_x: 643500
    origin_y: 4824500
    pixel_resolution: 3.125
    provider: "planetscope"
    published: "2019-01-19T17:06:09.990Z"
    rows: 8000
    satellite_id: "1010"
    strip_id: "2037910"
    sun_azimuth: 153.4
    sun_elevation: 21.8
    updated: "2019-01-20T04:21:04.837Z"
    usable_data: 0.83
    view_angle: 0.1
  type: "Feature"

```

Figure 5-3: PlanetScope Ortho Tile, JSON metadata file [RD-2].

In addition, where applicable, the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (**GDAL**) / OpenGIS Simple Feature Reference Implementation (**OGR**) library was used to access the metadata and retrieve / check the format specification, coordinate system, associated geometric transformation, additional metadata and band statistics demonstrating that the GeoTIFF format implementation of Planet complies with the standards.

It is worth noting that in the JSON file, the “**pixel_resolution**” is referring to the pixel spacing of the image map and the Ground Sampling Distance (**GSD**), which is perfectly correct.

It is in agreement with the definition of the GSD given in the Planet Imagery Product Specification document [RD-2], defining the GSD parameter as follows:

Ground Sample Distance (GSD)

The distance between pixel centres, as measured on the ground. It is mathematically calculated based on optical characteristics of the telescope, the altitude of the satellite, and the size and shape of the CCD sensor.

As defined in [Fiete 2001¹] and recalled below, the GSD is associated to the detector in the instrument, and can be related to the Ground Instantaneous Field of View (**GIFOV**), assuming a certain knowledge of the design (“fill factor”). As GSD is varying in the field of view, the GSD is basically given for a nadir viewing geometry.

The GSD is calculated by projecting the detector sampling pitch through the imaging system onto the ground. If the fill factor is 100% for each detector element then the GSD is equal to the ground instantaneous field of view (GIFOV), which is the linear extent of each detector projected onto the ground. The GSD in one dimension for a nadir viewing geometry is

$$GSD = p \frac{h}{f}$$

Where p is the detector pitch, h is the altitude of the satellite and f is the effective focal length of the optical system.

In two dimensions the GSD is commonly defined as the geometric mean of the x and y detector pitch projected to the ground. The x -axis is associated with the cross-scan direction of the array and the y -axis is associated with the along-scan direction. Because the GSD is the sampling distance projected onto the ground plane, the sampling distance along the line-of-sight increased.

This formula is also in agreement with the definition applied by Planet and reported in the CQC document [RD-19].

Note that in the XML Metadata file, the term ‘rowGsd’ / ‘columnGsd’ is referring to the pixel resolution of the image and is not referring to the GSD as discussed above. An extract of the XML metadata content is given below with the ‘Gsd’ word highlighted.

¹ Robert Fiete, Image Quality Assessment and $\lambda FN/p$ for remote sensing systems. 1999 Society of Photo-Optical, instrumentation Engineers. [S0091-3286(99)02107-8]

```

- <gml:resultOf>
- <ps:EarthObservationResult>
- <eop:product>
- <ps:ProductInformation>
  <eop:fileName>2037910_3159121_2019-01-19_1010_BGRN_Analytic.tif</eop:fileName>
  <ps:productFormat>GeoTIFF</ps:productFormat>
- <ps:spatialReferenceSystem>
  <ps:epsgCode>32631</ps:epsgCode>
  <ps:geodeticDatum>WGS_1984</ps:geodeticDatum>
  <ps:projection>WGS 84 / UTM zone 31N</ps:projection>
  <ps:projectionZone>31</ps:projectionZone>
</ps:spatialReferenceSystem>
  <ps:resamplingKernel>CC</ps:resamplingKernel>
  <ps:numRows>8000</ps:numRows>
  <ps:numColumns>8000</ps:numColumns>
  <ps:numBands>4</ps:numBands>
  <ps:rowGsd>3.125</ps:rowGsd>
  <ps:columnGsd>3.125</ps:columnGsd>
  <ps:radiometricCorrectionApplied>true</ps:radiometricCorrectionApplied>
  <ps:geoCorrectionLevel>Precision Geocorrection</ps:geoCorrectionLevel>
  <ps:elevationCorrectionApplied>FineDEM</ps:elevationCorrectionApplied>
  <ps:atmosphericCorrectionApplied>>false</ps:atmosphericCorrectionApplied>
</ps:ProductInformation>
</eop:product>

```

As conclusion, the tags 'rowGsd' / 'columnGsd' part of the PlanetScope namespace (PS) are not in agreement with the physical definition of the GSD as discussed above. Furthermore, there is an inconsistency with the JSON file content.

For information, the delivered ortho product is resampled using "cubic" convolution kernel from a 3.9 m GSD (Nadir) up to 3.125 m pixel resolution for all the images.

In general, the product format of the XML DIMAP file is detailed and conforms to the various OGC standards. Regarding the content of the metadata files, the fields are well documented with comments written into the XML.

XML Metadata file for Acquisition parameters

The PlanetScope products type analysed are "Ortho Tile". A tile is based on the UTM grid system [RD-2] and is defined as a 24 km by 24 km area, with 1 km buffer for a total of 25 km x 25 km tile.

One or more "Ortho Scene" images are included within the geographical extent of the "Ortho Tile". These images are stitched together in a transparent way for the user.

Figure 5-4: PlanetScope Ortho Tile Production [RD-2].

If a portion of the tile does not contain usable data, it is filled by dark background.

Typically, a PlanetScope Ortho Scene product acquired on a given date/time falls within several (up to 4) adjacent "Ortho Tiles". Consequently, when ordering neighbouring "Ortho Tile" products for a given region of interest, all data are from the same "Ortho Scene".

The acquisition parameters present in each tile metadata file are included in the **acquisitionParameters** xml tag and they are the following:

- orbitDirection
- incidenceAngle
- illuminationAzimuthAngle
- illuminationElevatonAngle
- azimuthAngle
- spaceCraftViewAngle
- acquisitionDateTime

It might be expected that the acquisition parameter metadata attached to each "Ortho Tile" reflects the observation geometry of the Tile. To check this hypothesis, the acquisition parameters of two adjacent "Ortho Tiles" (Tile 1, Tile 2) have been compared and are reported below.

```

Product           : 1709099_3452224_2018-09-19_0f22 (tile 1)
Product           : 1709099_3452223_2018-09-19_0f22 (tile 2)

Observation Date  : 2018-09-19T08:37:36.644437+00:00

Mission           : PlanetScope_0f22_LEO-SSO (Flock-3p 74 (DOVE
0F22)             2017-008DE 15.02.2017)

Instrument        : PS2

Data type         : L3A

Tile ID           : 3452224

Atms correction   : false

Radio correction  : true

Geo correction type : Precision Geocorrection

DEM correction type : FineDEM

Center Geo Coordinates

lat / lon (dd)    : 28.5149639005 / 23.3186173022

EPSG Code of the scene : 32634
  
```

1709099_3452223_2018-09-19_0f22 (tile 1) **1709099_3452224_2018-09-19_0f22 (tile 2)**

```

<ps:Acquisition>
<eop:orbitDirection>DESCENDING<
/eop:orbitDirection>
<eop:incidenceAngle uom="deg">
  
```

```

<ps:Acquisition>
<eop:orbitDirection>DESCENDING<
/eop:orbitDirection>
<eop:incidenceAngle uom="deg">
  
```

<pre> 2.083407e- 01</eop:incidenceAngle> <opt:illuminationAzimuthAngle uom="deg"> 1.331000e+02</opt:illuminationA zimuthAngle> <opt:illuminationElevationAngle uom="deg"> 5.350000e+01</opt:illuminationE levationAngle> <ps:azimuthAngle uom="deg">1.170000e+01</ps:azim uthAngle> <ps:spaceCraftViewAngle uom="deg"> 1.000000e- 01</ps:spaceCraftViewAngle> <ps:acquisitionDateTime> 2018-09- 19T08:37:36.644437+00:00</ps:ac quisitionDateTime> </ps:Acquisition> </pre>	<pre> 1.467581e- 01</eop:incidenceAngle> <opt:illuminationAzimuthAngle uom="deg"> 1.331000e+02</opt:illuminationA zimuthAngle> <opt:illuminationElevationAngle uom="deg"> 5.350000e+01</opt:illuminationE levationAngle> <ps:azimuthAngle uom="deg">1.170000e+01</ps:azim uthAngle> <ps:spaceCraftViewAngle uom="deg"> 1.000000e- 01</ps:spaceCraftViewAngle> <ps:acquisitionDateTime> 2018-09- 19T08:37:36.644437+00:00</ps:ac quisitionDateTime> </ps:Acquisition> </pre>
---	---

Comments in the XML Metadata file

In *bandSpecificMetadata* section, the following comment is written to describe the radiometricScaleFactor parameter.

```
<!-- Multiply by radiometricScaleFactor to convert DNs to TOA
Radiance (watts per steradian per square metre -->
```

It might indicate that the dimensions are not scaled by micrometers (bandwidth). The spectral radiance is usually expressed in watts per Meter² per Steradian per micrometers, SI: W·m⁻²·sr⁻¹·µm⁻¹.

However, in the full product specification document, it is stated that the Top of Atmosphere radiance is calculated in the usual dimensions W·m⁻²·sr⁻¹·µm⁻¹.

5.4 Image quality

The usability of satellite image for interpretation, or object detection and reconstruction purposes highly depends on the image quality. The image quality is characterized by a large number of quantitative measures such as the Point Spread Function (PSF), the MTF, SNR, and the GSD.

These parameters lead to a characterisation of the spatial response of an imager. These parameters are subsequently ingested in the estimate of the blur kernel. The blur kernel, so called transfer function, is a key item for calibration / validation activities and for image restoration (deconvolution).

In the context of this present study, for many reasons, the EDAP team has not focused on the assessment of these image quality quantitative measures. Rather, in the user perspective, efforts have been spent on the visual inspection of images and on the assessment of image interpretability.

5.4.1 Image quality measures

The section herein presents the main reasons for which the image quality of PlanetScope data has not been quantitatively assessed.

Several analyses on spatial resolution of PlanetScope have already been done. In [RD-21], as part of conclusions, it is mentioned the following important points:

- The MTF at Nyquist is above 0.2 in all cases and for all Level 1B products,
- Inconsistencies of results between the different Flocks,
- The RED product provides the best image performance,
- The Along Track MTF is degraded compared to the Across Track MTF.

Looking at CQC graphic outputs shown in the documentation, one can add the following points:

- The presence of aliasing visible in the Normalized Edge Spread Function (**ESF**) (visible in the figure below, top left graphic),
- The MTF shape is decreasing very quickly to reach 0.2 at Nyquist frequency, it is linked to aliasing,
- The SNR is low, and there is no linearity in the noise level,
- The smear due to satellite motion is important and explains the difference between the two Along and Across Track MTF results.

Figure 5-5: MTF CQC results - Green Band, 1B product.

As mentioned before, the blur kernel is a complex combination of several kernels; the optical blur, detector blur, satellite blur and, in the case of along track MTF, the motion blur. Moreover, when analysing ortho product, a geometric resampling kernel is added. The inversion of the model requires knowledge on the optics (relative aperture / transmission) and detector parameters (quantum efficiency, size, integration time, and time-delay integration stages). The data provider, Planet, does not disclose this information. Also, even if the computation of PSF / MTF is feasible, for reasons mentioned above, no MTF model can be fitted and therefore, the interpretation of MTF results is very limited.

Secondly, the MTF is a measure related to the sensor, also it is important ideally to use as input a product without geometric resampling applied (refer to MTF ALOS study). The L1B product is not available from the Planet catalogue. Planet MTF specification is given for L1B products.

Thirdly, the MTF assessment by using edge method [RD-22] and more particularly edge present in artificial target (checkboard) requires as input an image of target size including a significant number of lines and columns for an accurate estimate of the ESF. The SALON target is suitable for a sensor with a GSD below 2.5 m. As seen above, the GSD of PlanetScope is higher. It is obvious that with GSD bigger than 2.5 m, it is not possible to capture a representative number of Across Track and Along Track pixel phases. The figure below from [RD-17] gives the specification of the targets for an accurate estimate of PSF / MTF. The bigger target of Baoutou, should have been used.

↳ **Edge pattern (field transition, ice shelf,...)**

- ESF measurement
⇒ LSF estimation by deconvolution

$$M(f) \approx K \frac{H(f)}{f} + B(f)$$

- Rules of thumb :
 - $L_T >$ radius of the PSF extend (3/5 GSD)
Avoid background contamination
 - $L_W >$ diameter of the PSF extend (6/12 GSD)
Get the entire PSF contribution around the edge
 - $L_H >$ 20 GSD
 - Improvement of the SNR budget (stacking profiles)
 - Enable a sufficient oversampling of the profiles
 - Oversampling factor linked to α
 - The dark/bright contrast $>$ 50 x noise std. (with multi-look (TBC))

Figure 5-6: Rules of thumb for MTF estimate with “knife” edge method [RD-17].

It is worth noting that images of natural targets (coastlines) are particularly convenient for the MTF estimate. For instance, this approach is adopted in the context of the Sentinel-2 Mission Performance Centre (MPC) for monitoring of MTF. In the case of DOVE, no similar methodology has been implemented; in particular due to the noise of the method that is not correctly managed.

Fourthly, the quantity of data required to analyse MTF in the constellation context should be important and an appropriate methodology should be applied. Applying our method on few products is not relevant. As mentioned in [RD-19], there is an important variability of the measurements depending on the flock, on the satellite and on the period. Furthermore, in [RD-20], it is shown that the variations of image sharpness in the constellation do not solely depend on the satellite, but also other important factors such as the motion (stabilisation of the satellite) and the processing (i.e. Level 1C processing tends to degrade the sharpness).

Furthermore, it is also possible to extrapolate the quality of the product, based on optical system specifications, as the ones provided in the CQC report [RD-19].

As discussed in [RD-23], The ratio of the sampling frequency to the optical bandpass limit of an incoherent diffraction-limited optical system is a fundamental design parameter for digital imaging systems. This ratio is denoted by $\lambda FN/p$, where λ is the mean wavelength, FN is the system f /number, and p is the detector sampling pitch. The value of $\lambda FN/p$ for a remote sensing system can have a profound impact on the image quality and the utility of the acquired images. For the RGBN bands, the $\lambda FN/p$ of PlanetScope data is respectively 0.67, 0.76, 0.88, 1,14. It means that the spatial resolution is highly limited by the detector. Reducing $\lambda FN/p$ much below 1.0 can cause objectionable aliasing artefacts. On the other hand, reducing $\lambda FN/p$ increases the SNR. The SNR is controlled by the integration time (exposure).

A good SNR means that the integration time can be reduced and therefore the image smear contaminating some of PanetScope images is removed. It is the reason for which Planet monitors very closely the SNR and adapts the exposure time accordingly to what is described in the Planet Quality Report [RD-24].

Finally, the analysis of image quality can be performed qualitatively based on image interpretability techniques. Complementary to the visual inspection, the EDAP Team implemented the National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale (**NIIRS**) methodology. The NIIRS quantifies the interpretability of an image. Also, the advantages of this method are to assign a number which indicates the interpretability of a given image. The number is strongly related to SNR, MTF and other parameters, as shown in ². Also, if more information can be extracted from the image, then the NIIRS rating increases.

5.4.2 Visual inspection

The visual inspection allowed the discovery of high-level issues that were subsequently investigated in a quantitative analysis in the geometric and radiometric calibration sections.

The quality of the image in terms of noise, blur and striping is generally “Good”. In addition, a visual check of the geolocation showed that there are no large deviations compared to reference web map vectorial layer such as ‘Bing’ layer.

Also, the overall image quality and geolocation quality are generally “Good”. It is important to note that the assessment is related to the image, because quality strongly depends on the PlanetScope satellite considered, see section 5.5 for more details.

² Robert Fiete, :Image Quality Assessment and $\lambda FN/p$ for remoste sensing systems. 1999 Society of Photo-Optical, instrumentation Engineers. [S0091-3286(99)02107-8]

Figure 5-7: PlanetScope tile 3159121 over LaCrau true colour (left) and NIR false colour (right) composite.

Minor image artefacts due to mis-calibration or dead detector are observed, visible over homogenous/uniform parts of the image where image contrast is low. These errors are partially flagged by the Unusable Data Mask (**UDM**) present in each PlanetScope product. However, after the acquisition of the products, Planet has updated their data mask including a new asset called Usable Data Mask which was not available at the time of this analysis. For this reason, a full analysis of the cloud mask was not performed.

Hot pixels and saturations are often found as straight vertical lines. This effect is a known problem for PlanetScope data and it is due to the selected sensor type on board the satellite: “Interline Transfer CCD”³ sensor type.

In Interline transfer CCD sensors, each pixel has a charge storage area next to it. Interline Transfer CCD sensors avoid (minimise) image smear by the fact that the pixel storage area is masked so light cannot hit it. If they were not covered then photons hitting the storage area while a charge is being clocked down through that storage area, would have electrons added to it. This has an effect in an image that looks like and is called “smear”. If the image scene has a bright point, this bright point would be smeared vertically down the image⁴. The two image artefacts; saturation and smearing are shown in Figure 5-8. Smear happens at several locations in the image (indicated with orange arrows). Cross checking with the Quality Control (**QC**) mask, it is observed that:

- It is not all contaminated pixels that are flagged as corrupted,
- As a consequence of a bright target, pixels (below the bright target) are not totally reset and residual charges are causing vertical stripes in the image.
- The QC mask does not flag systematically the pixels contaminated by saturation or smears.

Note that the flagging algorithm of smear pixels is under review at Planet as hot columns are visible in over half of the PlanetScope images.

³ Communication with Arin Jumpasut, Planet Company (16/01/2020)

⁴ <http://www.adept.net.au/news/newsletter/200810-oct/sensors.shtml>

Figure 5-8: Piemonte PlanetScope true colour (left) and UDM (right) with white pixels (blue arrow) flagging a small number of corrupted pixels compared to the observation (orange arrow).

5.4.3 Rating scale

As mentioned above, to complement the visual inspection, EDAP Team implemented the NIIRS methodology.

The aerial imaging community utilizes the NIIRS to define and measure the quality of images and performance of imaging systems. Through a process referred to as "rating" an image, the NIIRS is used by imagery analysts to assign a number, which indicates the interpretability of a given image.

The NIIRS concept provides a means to directly relate the quality of an image to the interpretation tasks for which it may be used. Although the NIIRS has been primarily applied in the evaluation of aerial imagery, it provides a systematic approach to measuring the quality of photographic or digital imagery, the performance of image capture devices, and the effects of image processing algorithms⁵.

This activity is performed according to a well-defined procedure, which is based on photo interpretation of specific targets and the detection of visual anomalies in the data. As a result, besides known issues, this approach was used to provide an image quality score ("No good", "Good", Very Good") that is comparable across missions / product types, and is particularly important for VHR / HR images as they tend to be used for mapping at a higher cartographic scale (1:10000).

⁵ <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm>

As shown in the web page, the NIIRS rating scale is assessed according to a range of Ground Resolved Distance (**GRD**). For instance, a “NIIRS 2” rating scale corresponds to an image for which it is possible to:

- Detect multilane highways.
- Detect strip mining.
- Determine water current direction as indicated by colour differences (e.g., tributary entering larger water feature, chlorophyll or sediment patterns).
- Detect timber clear-cutting.
- Delineate extent of cultivated land.
- Identify riverine flood plains.

For more information on the NIIRS rating scale, see <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm>, an example of which is given in the table below.

Table 5-1 – NIIRS Rating Levels example, [RD-18]

Table 13.2 Examples of NIIRS Rating Levels	
NIIRS Value	Example Criteria
0	Imagery is uninterpretable
1	Distinguish between major land use classes (e.g., urban, agriculture, forest, water, barren)
2	Identify road patterns (e.g., clover leaf on major highway systems)
3	Detect individual houses in residential neighborhood
4	Count unoccupied railroad tracks along right-of-way in a rail yard
5	Identify individual rail cars by type (e.g., gondola, light box)
6	Identify automobiles as sedans or station wagons
7	Identify individual railroad ties
8	Identify windshield wipers on a vehicle
9	Detect individual spikes in a railroad

ALOS PRISM high resolution data (Image pixel resolution is 2.5 m) have been used as reference to compare recognisable ground feature objects. PRISM data is classified with a NIIRS between 2 and 3. Besides, the PlanetScope data has been assessed and a NIIRS in the range of 1 and 2 have been found.

The difference of GSD (image pixel resolution in this case) is only 0.6 m but in terms of image interpretation, the differences are important. Figures illustrating interpretability differences between ALOS PRISM and PlanetScope images are shown in the part dedicated to geometric activities (see Section 5.5).

In geometric activities, the identification of the GCP set is a manual operation. The same GCP should be recovered in both PRISM reference image and PlanetScope image. It has been observed that well defined GCPs in the reference image space cannot be fully recovered in the PlanetScope image. The problem was essentially due to image quality degradation caused by the motion blur.

5.5 Geometric Calibration / Validation

5.5.1 Activity Description Sheet

Geometric Accuracy Validation: Absolute geolocation / Multitemporal geolocation / Interband registration
<p><u>Inputs</u></p> <p>Set of Level 3A PlanetScope (DOVE) data (subset of products listed in APPENDIX B)</p>
<p><u>Description</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimate the geometric accuracy of PlanetScope products including absolute geolocation, accuracy, multi temporal geolocation accuracy and inter-band registration accuracy. Verify that the measured accuracy is within the product specification accuracy, as stated in the product specification document [RD-2]: product Absolute / Multi temporal registration RMSE accuracy is within 10.0 m. For the assessment of the absolute geolocation error, a semi-automatic comparison of the PlanetScope imagery with a set of GCPs was used. The set of GCPs was collected <i>in situ</i> with GPS measurements in previous validation campaigns and it was refined to obtain the accuracy of each GCP within 0.2 cm. However, the pointing accuracy (i.e. the accuracy of the positioning of the GCPs in the image space) strongly depends on the image quality. <p>For the assessment of multi temporal geolocation and inter-band registration accuracy, the outputs from dense matching techniques (based on Normalized Cross Correlation algorithms) was used and it was compared to the internal image geometry of two images. While the multi temporal activity is focused on a set of temporal PlanetScope images and it compares to the same band acquired at different times, the inter-band activity is focused on comparing different bands belonging to the same product (i.e. acquired at the same time); all delivered products are considered.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-band accuracy: the product RMSE accuracy is within 0.2 pixels for band twins (1,2) and (2,3) while it is 0.35 pixels for the twin (3,4).
<p><u>Outputs</u></p> <p>Geometric accuracy metrics.</p>

5.5.2 Tools

The image matching was performed by using the CNES Medicis Tool [RD-15] with specific configuration applied to ingest PlanetScope data. An important post processing step is to remove the outliers, to analyse deformation and generate the quality metrics in the output.

5.5.3 Regions of interest

The regions of interest for the geometric accuracy evaluation are La Crau (south of France (FR)), Piemonte (Italy (IT)), Adana (Turkey (TU)) and Wellington (South Africa (SAFR)). The regions of interest were identified based on the availability of geometric reference dataset (in situ GCP set, reference raster products). The full extent of the PlanetScope acquisition was considered, if more than one tile was present for a given product, they were mosaicked together to form a single image.

Figure 5-9: La Crau Test Field with *in situ* GCPs set Spatial Distribution.

5.5.4 PlanetScope Data

All the products analysed were PlanetScope PS2 on sun-synchronous orbit launched in 2017 in two different flocks, namely Flock-3p and Flock-2k. The PlanetScope Satellite ID is part of the products identifier code. By cross-referencing the satellite ID with the Flock launches, it was possible to retrieve the Flock number for each product used. The breakdown is as follows:

- Flock-3p: 1010 / 101b /1042, 1044 (Launch date 15-02-2017)
- Flock-2k: 104b, 1053 series (Launch date 14-07-2017)

Full information on PlanetScope satellites is provided in APPENDIX A.

The products included in the geometric analysis are listed in the table below. Note that for one product code, several tiles are delivered. The tiles are carefully stitched to create a single input image to cover the geographic extent of the test site.

Table 5-2 - PlanetScope data used to perform the assessment of geometric accuracy.

Product acquisition date (satellite ID)	Site	Country
2018-12-31 (1053)	Piemont	IT
2018-11-25 (1044)	Adana	TU
2018-12-28 (1042)	Wellington	SAFR
2018-11-30 (104b)	Wellington	SAFR
2019-01-30 (101b)	La Crau	FR
2019-01-19 (1010)	La Crau	FR

5.5.5 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy

5.5.5.1 Methods

The absolute geolocation accuracy was estimated by using three reference sets of GCPs collected during a GPS test field survey undertaken during the ALOS Optical Instrument Calibration / Validation phase [RD-3, RD-15]. The following sites have been covered:

- La Crau (France)
- Piemont (Italy)
- Wellington (South Africa)

The analysis was divided into two steps, the first consisted of the identification of each in situ GCP available in the test product (the PlanetScope image). The second step consisted of the estimation of the different map positioning of the in situ and image space GCP. A semi-automatic method allows identifying well-defined GCPs in the PlanetScope image. The absolute geolocation accuracy with geo-positional accuracy statistics are shown below.

5.5.5.2 Results

To perform this assessment, the input image band with the best contrast has been taken as input. It is important to note that due to image quality, the GCP pointing accuracy, which is the accuracy in identifying the in situ GCPs in the image space, is not optimal.

The upsampling of the PlanetScope image grid from ~4 m to 3.125 m dilutes the Digital Number (**DN**) difference over some natural and manmade objects and does not allow to recognise these objects, which are typically recognised at this spatial resolution. This limitation, in terms of image interpretability, has direct impact on GCP pointing accuracy (see section 5.4).

The two figures below show a comparison between ALOS PRISM and PlanetScope images. It was estimated an error of about -3.7 m and 5.78 m in the Easting and Northing direction, respectively. The contrast is low compared to ALOS PRISM image data (2.5 m GSD), as reported in Figure 5-10 and Figure 5-11.

Figure 5-10: GCP position (red dot) over Wellington image PlanetScope 1973356_3423606_2018-12-28_1042_BGRN_Analytic (Red band, 3.125 m GSD)

Figure 5-11: GCP position (green) over Wellington image (ALOS PRISM, panchromatic, 2.5 m GSD)

The absolute geolocation results are listed in Table 5-3. The precision is generally within 1 pixel, with a strong degradation concerning the La Crau products. The accuracy is correct

(i.e. within the product specification document requirement for the mission) and is maintained roughly within 1.5 pixel. The quality assurance metrics (RMSE, Circular Error (CE)) tell us that:

- Geometric Quality of Piedmont data is correct, even in presence of steep relief,
- Geometric Quality of La Crau data is correct, it is worth noting a circular error above 10.0 m despite the high precision,
- Geometric Quality of Wellington data is correct but shows a degradation of accuracy (more than 1 pixel) in the along-track direction.

Due to the variability observed and the limited number of products analysed, we cannot conclude that the geometric quality is stable across the mission. However, the absolute geolocation accuracy computed in the EDAP assessment is in agreement with the product accuracy specification given by Planet.

Table 5-3 Absolute geometric accuracy results (meters).

	Piemont (It)	LaCrau (FR)	Wellington (SA)
GCP #sample	14	17	16
meanX (m)	-2,77	-2,89	-2,50
meanY (m)	-1,25	0,00	4,24
stdX (m)	4,23	5,54	2,53
stdY (m)	3,51	6,48	4,23
RMSX (m)	3,04	2,89	4,92
RMSY (m)	3,72	6,48	5,99
RMS (m)	4,81	7,09	7,75
ce90 (m)	8,58	11,65	9,76

Figure 5-12: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy - Circular Error Plot (Piedmont).

Figure 5-13: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy - Circular Error Plot (La Crau).

Figure 5-14: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy - Circular Error Plot (Wellington).

5.5.6 Multi-temporal Geolocation Accuracy

5.5.6.1 Methods

The multi-temporal geolocation accuracy is a critical parameter, notably for any application purposes related to spatio-temporal analysis. Whilst the previous assessment considered a sparse sample of manually collected ground control point sets, this assessment compares geometry of two PlanetScope images observed at two different dates over the same area. If the internal geometry of images is correct and does not change with time, the registration accuracy is high. For example, reference missions have geometric registration within one pixel (less than 0.3 pixel in case of Landsat 8 / OLI and 12 m (CE95) for Sentinel 2 MSI).

In the following section, the geometry is compared by using dense matching techniques (ZNCC algorithms). Post processing for selecting a sample is conducted and an accuracy analysis performed. The assessment for multi temporal geolocation accuracy was performed on all four bands (Blue, Green, Red, NIR). It was necessary to assess all the bands separately as many users are interested in temporal metrics derived from band operations (Vegetation indexes for example). The multi-temporal displacement of the image pair was calculated independently along the image lines (North-South) also known as “line direction” and the image columns (East-West) also known as “pixel direction”.

The test sites for this validation exercise are La Crau (FR) and Wellington (SAFR).

5.5.6.2 Results

5.5.6.2.1 Overall Results

The test sites for this validation exercise are La Crau (FR) and Wellington (SAFR). The mean and standard deviation of the multitemporal geometric accuracy are listed in Table 5-4.

Table 5-4 Multitemporal geometric accuracy results (planimetric, pixels).

LaCrau					
Band	sample_pixel	mean_x	std_x	mean_y	std_y
Band 1	267067	0.10	0.68	-0.06	0.76
Band 2	436579	0.10	0.61	-0.03	0.71
Band 3	405365	0.10	0.64	-0.01	0.72
Band 4	498926	0.26	0.89	0.52	1.03
Wellington					
Band	sample_pixel	mean_x	std_x	mean_y	std_y
Band 1	594934	-0.06	0.55	-0.24	0.60
Band 2	941370	-0.01	0.56	-0.25	0.60
Band 3	856697	0.13	0.61	-0.22	0.66
Band 4	445537	-0.13	1.20	-0.15	1.01

5.5.6.2.2 La Crau site

For BGR bands, the mean accuracy in pixel direction is really good with 0.05 m. The accuracy in line direction remains low (< 0.25 m). The precision is below 2.0 m.

For NIR band, probably due to image quality, the precision is at pixel level (~3.0 m), which is high. The circular error at 90th percentile for NIR is high (5.68 m).

Figure 5-15: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (La Crau).

Figure 5-16: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (La Crau).

Figure 5-17: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (La Crau).

Figure 5-18: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (La Crau).

Figure 5-19: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (La Crau).

Figure 5-20: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (La Crau).

Figure 5-21: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (La Crau).

Figure 5-22: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (La Crau).

Figure 5-23: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (La Crau).

Figure 5-24: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 4 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (La Crau).

Figure 5-25: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 4 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (La Crau).

Figure 5-26: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 4 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (La Crau).

5.5.6.2.3 Wellington site

The results over Wellington are similar although the satellites involved are different.

The accuracy is correct, the precision varies depending on spectral bands, with major issues concerning the NIR band. The accuracy in the pixel direction is stable across the spectral band and is 0.65 m, which means there is a systematic bias of 1/5 pixel. The accuracy in line direction varies across spectral bands up to 0.6 m. The BGR precision is below 2.0 m.

For the NIR band the precision is above 3.0 m in both directions, which is about 1 pixel. The circular error for NIR is large (6.76 m) compared to BGR (< 3.50 m).

Figure 5-27: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (Wellington).

Figure 5-28: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (Wellington).

Figure 5-29: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 1 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (Wellington).

Figure 5-30: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north-south direction (lines) (Wellington).

Figure 5-31: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (Wellington).

Figure 5-32: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 2 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (Wellington).

Figure 5-33: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (Wellington).

Figure 5-34: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (Wellington).

Figure 5-35: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (Wellington).

Figure 5-36: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 4 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the north south direction (lines) (Wellington).

Figure 5-37: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 4 Histogram of multi-temporal displacement along the east west direction (pixel) (Wellington).

Figure 5-38: Multi-Temporal Geolocation Accuracy – Band 3 Scatterplot of multi-temporal displacement and CE90 (green circle) (Wellington).

5.5.6.2.4 Early investigation on internal geometric issues

By checking the disparity maps output from the multi temporal accuracy assessments, strong geometric distortions in the images have been detected. These distortions are not linear and are not directly observed in the overall results presented just here before. Also, the scope of this part is to provide a first analysis of the anomaly observed.

For the La Crau site, a same flock, 'Flock-3p', is involved in the data acquisition of the scenes whereas for Wellington site, there are two different flocks involved (Flock-3p / Flock-2p).

As for results detailed before, the input dataset type is Planet Ortho tile products. It is required to reconstruct data observed in the full extent of the field of view in order to maximise information to be matched. In this perspective, the images from the two adjacent tiles observed at the same date / time are stitched.

The two following figures show the two La Crau's NIR band stitched images corresponding to the two different dates respectively in 19/01/2019 and in 30/01/2019.

Figure 5-39 - Flock-3p 10 (DOVE 1010) – two ortho tile images are stitched to create a full image before geometric assessment processing (#320720 / #320721).

Figure 5-40 - Flock-3p 60 (DOVE 101B) –the two ortho tile images are stitched to create a full image before geometric assessment processing (#320722 / #320723).

Dense matching compares the two input image grids and output two disparity maps related to the displacements in the pixel and line direction. The results for La Crau NIR band images are shown in Figure 5-41. Local deformations are in both pixel and line displacement images. The error (line direction/ pixel direction) varies in the range of [-2, +2] pixels and is more pronounced in the pixel direction. The Figure 5-42 confirms that the issue is not observed in the BLUE / GREEN / RED image bands. For the NIR images, the internal geometry in the tile is not stable; and the error is changing suddenly in the north / south direction at a constant time.

Figure 5-41: Disparity map when comparing two Plant Ortho tiles image grid. (unit of measure: pixel).

Figure 5-42: Radial errors when comparing two Plant Ortho tiles image grid. The Ortho scene boundary is only visible in the NIR images. Parallax errors are visible for all image bands (unit of measure: pixel).

Referring to Figure 5-4, the geolocation accuracy varies at the transition between two Ortho Scenes. The Ortho tile image is generated from a collection of Ortho scenes, typically 4 to 5. Figure 5-42 shows also that the geometric deformation within a scene is related to parallax errors, because the difference in the orientation of the respective Ortho Tiles: the parallax errors are observed in all bands.

The two observations over La Crau have been performed with two different cross-track off-nadir angles. The parallax error is a residual error of the ortho processing meaning the elevation information used by Planet is perhaps not appropriate. If the structure of the relief is recovered in the disparity map, it means that the not-systematic effects are not fully corrected by the Planet Ortho processing. Note that the pointing angles of the PlanetScope image pair used are 0.1° (19/01/2019) and 5° (30/01/2019) respectively.

Figure 5-43: Relationship between radial error magnitude and terrain relief for the NIR images, the boundaries of the scene has been added (green line).

The same analysis has been performed with images from the Wellington sites. The two images are acquired with the same viewing angles (about 2.0°), discarding any hypothesis of parallax error due to different viewing angles.

As for La Crau, the location of the ortho scene boundary remains visible in the disparity map as shown in Figure 5-44 and Figure 5-45. The issue affects all the bands and not only the NIR band as previously. The geometric deformations are mostly pronounced in line direction and can be up to 2.5 pixels.

Figure 5-44: Left) Line displacement image as output of matching between NIR Images. The error depends on the location of the respective Ortho Scenes (Wellington, unit of measure: pixel) Right) Ortho Scene footprint for the two dates (Green (30/11/2018), Red (28/12/2018)).

In the pixel displacement image (left image below), the patterns of the terrain relief, two hills located at the bottom left and at the upper right of the scene are also visible.

Figure 5-45: Left) Pixel displacement image as output of matching between NIR Images. The error depends on the location of the respective Ortho Scenes (Wellington, unit of measure: pixel). Right) Ortho Scene footprint for the two dates (Green (30/11/2018), Red (28/12/2018)).

The Wellington results are therefore worse compared to the La Crau results. It might be due to the generation of Flock involved, which is older in case of Wellington or it might be due to the location of the sites.

Note that even if the two observations have been made in descending orbit (according to product metadata (XML DIMAP) and orbit information from external tool), the viewing azimuth at the scene centre for the two different scenes are different: $12^\circ / 348^\circ$. Moreover, the orientation of both scenes is very different. One scene would correspond to an observation performed with a satellite operating in ascending orbit.

This early investigation has shown shortcomings related to the use of CCD frame-based array for data recording: a rigidity is achieved at scene level (one frame), the situation becomes more complex when mosaicking all scenes to create a bigger geographical extent product.

The frame images are taken at one single position in time, have one single acquisition position and one single bundle of projection rays. One frame image is the composite of two Tap images and so in a single image frame, two perspective centres exist on both sides of the image, it is probably the cause of the parallax observed.

Figure 5-46: PlanetScope Frames & Taps arrangements, with only one perspective centre per Tap (blue for RGB Taps), one frame is the composting of two Taps (red).

5.5.7 Inter-band Registration Accuracy

5.5.7.1 Methods

The inter-band geometric registration accuracy assessment relies on the following principles:

- Compare geometry between two image bands by using dense matching technics
- Evaluate geometric registration for the following bands combinations: (Blue, Green), (Green, Red), (Red, NIR), (NIR, Blue)
- Compute error budget, per site analysis and output global statistics
- All Sites considered (Libya, La Crau, Piemont, Adana, Wellington. Note that eventually, the Adana test site was removed from the analysis due to problems with the GCP set)

For each band pair the ZNCC algorithm estimates the band pair displacement in the sample (X) and line (Y) direction. The cross-correlation generates a confidence measure at pixel level for a subset of the image. The total number of pixels used to compute the cross-correlation are reported as “Total valid pixels” in Table 5-5. Only the pixels having a confidence level greater or equal to 0.9 are retained. The displacement estimated for the pixel retained are used to calculate the following summary metrics: minimum, median, mean, standard deviation and maximum value. The total number of pixels used to generate the statistics are reported as “Sample pixels” in Table 5-5. The error budget (orange lines, Table 5-5) was also estimated as the sum of the mean displacement over all the band pairs. The error budget is indicative of the uncertainty associated with the estimated measures.

The results of the inter-band exercise strongly depend on the test site used. Also, final results will be selected based on error budget attached to the site and observation date.

5.5.7.2 Results

Table 5-5 summarises the inter-band geometric registration accuracy results, which are also plotted in Figure 5-47.

Table 5-5: Band-to-band geometric registration accuracy results (pixel unit), for a correlation confidence of 0.9

PRODUCT	REF BAND	WORK BAND	Band_Pair	total valid pixel	sample pixel	confidence_th	min_x	max_x	median_x	mean_x	std_x	min_y	max_y	median_y	mean_y	std_y
13_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320729	4	1	4_1	6012	2058	0,9	-4,74219	4,99219	0,0078125	0,062856839	1,557257666	-4,74219	4,99219	-0,0703125	-0,098362336	1,479872878
13_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320729	1	2	1_2	18126	4941	0,9	-0,585938	0,640625	0	0,000196064	0,125435363	-0,65625	3,30469	0	0,004400362	0,13729164
13_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320729	2	3	2_3	19446	7096	0,9	-1,38281	1,38281	0	-0,002669858	0,165714268	-4,07812	4,48438	0,015625	0,015649221	0,278103713
13_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320729	3	4	3_4	8539	3227	0,9	-4,99219	4,98438	0	0,015317536	1,535236068	-4,98438	4,99219	-0,0546875	-0,077246185	1,448926815
Error Budget																
14_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320730	4	1	4_1	6868	2360	0,9	-4,86719	4,92969	0,0390625	0,120577331	1,672283643	-4,99219	4,67969	-0,08984375	-0,145815678	1,484584341
14_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320730	1	2	1_2	17319	4439	0,9	-1,21094	1,14062	0	0,001818047	0,142623753	-3,24219	4,41406	0,0078125	0,013662635	0,198773187
14_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320730	2	3	2_3	18478	6198	0,9	-1,52344	1,27344	0	-0,002988615	0,183223289	-4,22656	4,57031	0,0234375	0,043198159	0,331717099
14_Lybia4_PSC_planet_order_320730	3	4	3_4	9451	3524	0,9	-4,99219	4,99219	-0,0078125	-0,032307481	1,607069279	-4,51562	4,61719	-0,1171875	-0,156447308	1,532085152
Error Budget																
17_Piemont_PSC_planet_order_320734	4	1	4_1	4505	646	0,9	-4,49219	4,99219	0,06640625	0,189495453	1,41289274	-4,99219	4,19531	0,1796875	0,238631966	1,271298614
17_Piemont_PSC_planet_order_320734	1	2	1_2	15688	5932	0,9	-0,507812	0,539062	0,015625	0,016183412	0,117125694	-0,570312	1,50781	0	0,003308328	0,113955618
17_Piemont_PSC_planet_order_320734	2	3	2_3	18421	8932	0,9	-0,765625	0,765625	0	-0,004476531	0,134788206	-4,99219	2,42969	0	-0,00466196	0,145632881
17_Piemont_PSC_planet_order_320734	3	4	3_4	6337	1700	0,9	-4,42969	4,4375	-0,0625	-0,058405331	1,266368926	-4,99219	4,99219	-0,23828125	-0,235900735	1,206144987
Error Budget																
/4_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320720	4	1	4_1	6131	1681	0,9	-4,67969	4,50781	0,0390625	0,142797003	2,931175566	-15,546882	13,125	-0,05859375	0,001377599	2,737032101
/4_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320720	1	2	1_2	17123	9631	0,9	-0,539062	0,507812	0	-0,000136279	0,128609279	-0,554688	0,65625	0	-0,000967741	0,114998352
/4_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320720	2	3	2_3	19238	11655	0,9	-0,617188	0,617188	0	-0,002254934	0,134896415	-0,84375	0,585938	0	-0,002641704	0,120329489
/4_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320720	3	4	3_4	7540	2684	0,9	-4,08594	4,11719	-0,0234375	-0,071235213	1,134413696	-4,99219	4,29688	-0,03125	-0,134512388	1,099346643
Error Budget																
7_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320723	4	1	4_1	4464	1009	0,9	-4,35938	4,41406	-0,0859375	-0,152796705	1,313346689	-4,45312	4,99219	-0,1171875	-0,20606727	1,35848522
7_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320723	1	2	1_2	14696	7732	0,9	-0,617188	0,578125	0	0,004062864	0,127826308	-0,59375	0,742188	0	0,001641918	0,116976614
7_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320723	2	3	2_3	16189	9651	0,9	-0,601562	0,59375	-0,0078125	-0,008539432	0,133786077	-3,09375	0,992188	0	-0,000766598	0,131685217
7_LaCrau_PSC_planet_order_320723	3	4	3_4	5580	1738	0,9	-4,25781	4,28906	0,078125	0,021652942	1,180359164	-4,99219	4,99219	0,1640625	0,195424878	1,321191467
Error Budget																
18_Adana_PSC_planet_order_320735	4	1	4_1	3541	954	0,9	-4,99219	4,99219	-0,2578125	-0,3078731	1,983093847	-4,99219	4,99219	-0,015625	0,130953551	2,055315606
18_Adana_PSC_planet_order_320735	1	2	1_2	15404	6754	0,9	-0,578125	0,53125	0	-0,001900494	0,123693724	-0,648438	0,585938	-0,0078125	-0,007921232	0,117023502
18_Adana_PSC_planet_order_320735	2	3	2_3	18272	9049	0,9	-0,679688	0,71875	0,0078125	0,010541565	0,134234942	-4,49219	4,42969	0	-0,002567618	0,162659484
18_Adana_PSC_planet_order_320735	3	4	3_4	4328	1409	0,9	-4,99219	4,99219	0,4375	0,421059927	1,90584274	-4,99219	4,99219	-0,0859375	-0,239276526	1,994080229
Error Budget																
22_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320739	4	1	4_1	10742	3118	0,9	-4,25781	4,27344	-0,5	-0,121827898	4,150606786	-15,125008	15,000008	-0,118811825	-0,080902035	2,547637937
22_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320739	1	2	1_2	20712	16716	0,9	-0,5	0,5	0	-0,476943353	1,303268056	-4,99219	4,99219	0,0546875	0,044246612	1,20107353
22_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320739	2	3	2_3	20797	18289	0,9	-0,570312	0,570312	-0,0078125	-0,000923984	0,129277421	-0,859375	0,664062	0	-0,003990376	0,119404342
22_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320739	3	4	3_4	12406	4765	0,9	-4,71094	4,63281	0,4921875	0,482643625	1,247284523	-4,85156	4,80469	-0,0546875	-0,057173072	1,088313294
Error Budget																
23_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320740	4	1	4_1	9915	2989	0,9	-3,94531	3,94531	-0,375	-0,02350178	2,82186816	-13,820315	13,164062	-0,0078125	-0,008090235	2,547637937
23_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320740	1	2	1_2	18859	15999	0,9	-0,445312	0,445312	0,03125	-0,41909397	1,150342171	-4,99219	4,67969	-0,1640625	-0,130305913	1,05527304
23_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320740	2	3	2_3	18866	16883	0,9	-0,539062	0,617188	0,0703125	0,028279111	0,110999921	-0,820312	1,19531	0,0078125	0,004379668	0,102703884
23_Wellin_PSC_planet_order_320740	3	4	3_4	11417	4398	0,9	-4,24219	4,24219	0,234375	0,067562415	0,131363256	-1,61719	1,40625	0,0234375	0,021686941	0,123198331
Error Budget																
										-0,020295133	2,4701648	-12,421882	12,27344	-0,015625	0,009404327	2,210692687

Figure 5-47: Band-to-band registration accuracy results (pixel unit)

In general, we systematically observe a better centring accuracy for the band twins 1,2 & 2,3 and a degraded accuracy for band twins 3,4 and 4,1 (Table 5-6).

Table 5-6: Band-to-band geometric registration accuracy results summary (pixel unit)

Bands	Mean Line Displacement	Mean Pixel Displacement
(1,2)	0.007	-0.001
(2,3)	0.009	0.003
(3,4)	0.183	-0.060
(1,4)	-0.178	0.019

The accuracy / precision of results strongly depends on the test site. For instance, the estimated error budget associated with centring accuracy varies from <0.01 to a maximum value of 0.14 pixel in line direction and a maximum of 0.25 pixel in pixel direction.

Also, a finer interpretation is brought with the analysis of the Wellington data. For these two products, the sample size is significant (large number of pixels have been successfully matched and for those pixels the confidence value is high (above 0.9)) and error budget is within 0.02 pixel in both directions, indicating low uncertainty in the estimation in the worst case considered.

For the two Wellington products, the precision is within 1 pixel, the same behaviour is observed; its magnitude changes slightly depending on the observation date or satellite:

- For image twin into band sequence (1, 2, 3), Pixel Displacement is within 0.02 pixel in the worst case,
- For image twin into band sequence (1, 2, 3), Line Displacement is within 0.07 pixel in the worst case,

- For image twin (4,1) & (3,4), Pixel Displacement is within 0.13 pixel (absolute value) in the worst case,
- For image twin (4,1) & (3,4), Line Displacement is within 0.4 pixel (absolute value) in the worst case.

These latter statements are illustrated with the figure above (4,1) and (3,4) error values are mostly of an opposite sign.

5.6 Radiometric Calibration / Validation: Cross calibration between PlanetScope AND SENTINEL-2 MSI / LANDSAT 8 OLI data over PICS

5.6.1 Activity Description Sheet

Radiometric Accuracy Validation
<p><u>Inputs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set of Level 1C Sentinel-2 / MSI and Landsat 8 / OLI data • Set of Level 1 PlanetScope data
<p><u>Description</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was estimated the calibration ratio between PlanetScope data and the reference Sentinel-2A/2B mission, • The goal is to verify the cross calibration between the two sensors and to verify that the temporal stability of the radiometric accuracy within few days is within 15 %, as per product specification. • The PICS were used as internationally recognised for radiometric calibration studies.
<p><u>Outputs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross calibration ratio

5.6.2 Introduction

It was performed a cross comparison of radiometric calibration over PICS using as reference missions such as Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 Top-Of-Atmosphere (TOA) data. PICS have been identified by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellite (CEOS) for performing radiometric calibration / validation activities. For PlanetScope, the Libya-4 test site was used; the site is located in the Libyan Desert in Africa at coordinates +28.55° N and +23.39° W, with a terrain elevation of about 118 m above sea level.

The Libya-4 site was first proposed for SPOT calibration [RD-7] and demonstrated potential to be utilised for low, medium and high resolution optical visible and near infrared data [RD-2, RD-8, RD-9, RD-10, RD-11]. It is categorised as a “bright” site that, as discussed in [RD-12] within the context of reflectance-based methods, is characterised by high reflectance in conjunction with low aerosol loading and a predominance of clear skies that reduces the

impact of atmospheric errors. Other important aspects are the near Lambertian reflectance, the spectral and spatial uniformity and the temporal stability.

5.6.3 Methods and Tools

5.6.3.1 Methods

- 1) Visual inspection and comparison of Planet images with Sentinel-2 or Landsat-8 performed on two composites:
 - a. RGB True colour composition
 - b. RGB NIR false colour composition
- 2) Comparison of band histograms and statistics (min, max, mean, std)
- 3) Cross calibration methodology including the diffusion angle parameter

5.6.3.2 Tools

Tools are mostly in-house based on ad-hoc scripts.

5.6.4 Region of interest

The region of interest is within the Libya 4 CEOS site extent, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 5-48: Libya 4 region of interest (blue) and Landsat 8 full frame (grey).

Two PlanetScope products acquired on different dates have been considered for this exercise. In addition to the images (red, blue), the area selected to generate the cross-comparison statistics is depicted in Figure 5-49. Note that the presence of dunes produces areas with alternatively darker and brighter pixels oriented along track. The radiometric noise increases the uncertainty on radiometric calibration accuracy.

Figure 5-49: Planet NIR Images, extent of the statistical ROIs, with Landsat 8 data as background image.

The two PlanetScope images (Blue, Red) do not fully overlay the CEOS calibration region. Also, the geographic extent of the PlanetScope scenes slightly changes depending on the observation date: the overlapping portion of the two acquisition was used. The small vector polygon in Red depicts the ROI selected for cross calibration exercise.

5.6.4.1 Planet Data

- 2018-09-21T08:37:17.198099+00:00
- 2018-09-19T08:37:36.644437+00:00

5.6.4.2 Landsat Data

- LC08_L1TP_181040_20180921_20180928_01_T1
- LC81810402017165MTI00

5.6.4.3 Sentinel-2 Data

A 6 month period of acquisition was considered for both Sentinel-2A and -2B.

Table 5-7 Sentinel-2A and -2B used for cross calibration.

Product Observation Date	Day of Year	Mission
20180707T085601	188	S2A
20180717T085601	198	S2A
20180727T085601	208	S2A

Product Observation Date	Day of Year	Mission
20180806T085601	218	S2A
20180816T085551	228	S2A
20180826T085551	238	S2A
20180905T085551	248	S2A
20180925T085711	268	S2A
20181015T085931	288	S2A
20181025T090031	298	S2A
20181104T090131	308	S2A
20181114T090221	318	S2A
20181124T090301	328	S2A
20180702T085559	183	S2B
20180712T085559	193	S2B
20180722T085559	203	S2B
20180801T090019	213	S2B
20180811T085549	223	S2B
20180821T085549	233	S2B
20180831T085549	243	S2B
20180910T085549	253	S2B
20180920T085619	263	S2B
20181010T090019	283	S2B
20181020T085959	293	S2B
20181030T090109	303	S2B
20181109T090159	313	S2B
20181119T090249	323	S2B
20181129T090319	333	S2B

5.6.5 Prediction Model Estimation

The observation geometry of Planet data and Sentinel-2 / Landsat 8 data are not exactly similar. Furthermore, by having a long time series of Sentinel-2 / Landsat 8 against two observation dates of Planet data, the purpose of the proposed method compares the TOA reflectance of PlanetScope products with the predicted TOA of LS08 / S2 in the same acquisition day for a reference spectral band.

The proposed method does not account for relative spectral response band difference and atmospheric conditions.

The directional effect has been estimated by regressing the physical TOA measurements against the diffusion angle (the angle between the sun vector and the sensor-target direction), essentially used in the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) modelling.

Due to the narrow field of view with observation close to NADIR observation, the BRDF varies linearly, illustrated in Figure 5-50 showing, for each spectral band, the linear dependency of the TOA reflectance values against the scattering (diffusion) values). The coefficients of the linear model are shown directly in the graph. The linear model has been built by using as input the 29 clear sky Sentinel-2 MSI data, listed in the previous table.

It is therefore possible to account for BRDF effects and estimate the top of atmosphere value at the time of the Planet product observation for the concerned ROI.

Note that because of calibration accuracy differences, the two S2A/S2B samples have been distinguished and the cross-calibration exercise, Planet / Sentinel-2, was performed for the two different S2 satellites separately.

It is worth noting that the LS08 data have been used in both the comparison with Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B. As the calibration ratio between S2 and LS08 is well known, the LS08 / S2 results are mostly used to check the accuracy of the proposed methods.

Figure 5-50 shows (blue dots) the measurements reduced over the Libya 4 region shown in Figure 5-49. The reference S2 measurements are shown in yellow and grey; the control data from LS08 is in orange.

Figure 5-50: TOA Directional model with S2, LS08 and Planet Observation

5.6.6 Cross calibration Statistics

As explained above, the linear model coefficients are used to predict the TOA reflectance at the Planet DOVE observation geometries. In doing so, the simulated Planet DOVE data (S2/LS08 data) is compared with the input Planet DOVE data. The calibration ratios for the following twins are listed in Table 5-8 below:

- S2A / PlanetScope & S2B / PlanetScope
- S2A / LS08 & S2B / LS08

The results are temporally consistent; with two PlanetScope satellites, the intercalibration with Sentinel and Landsat does not change.

The agreement with Sentinel 2 measurements is within:

- 17% for the BLUE band,
- 3% for the GREEN and RED bands,
- 5% for the NIR bands,

These results should be mitigated because, for the GREEN and RED bands, the spectral band definition of PlanetScope is very different compared to that of Sentinel-2. The matching of spectral response curve is better for the BLUE and NIR bands. The spectral responses of PlanetScope DOVE are discussed in 5.7 and are used in the inter calibration approach.

Table 5-8: Cross Calibration statistical Results DOVE / S2A, DOVE / S2B.

		S2A			S2B		
Spectral bands	Item	Planet Date 1	Planet Date 2	LS08 Date 1	Planet Date 1	Planet Date 2	LS08 Date 1
	Diffusion Angle (dd)	37,10	36,55	31,83	37,10	36,55	31,830
Blue	S2 Predict	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25	0,25
	Test data	0,29	0,30	0,24	0,29	0,30	0,243
	Ratio	1,1748	1,1843	0,9677	1,1622	1,1719	0,959
Green	S2 Predict	0,33	0,33	0,33	0,33	0,33	0,33
	Test data	0,34	0,34	0,33	0,34	0,34	0,332
	Ratio	1,0305	1,0300	0,9982	1,0407	1,0404	0,9997
Red	S2 Predict	0,4652	0,4654	0,4673	0,4638	0,4642	0,4675
	Test data	0,4527	0,4570	0,4561	0,4527	0,4570	0,456
	Ratio	0,9732	0,9821	0,9762	0,9760	0,9845	0,9757
NIR (B8A)	S2 Predict	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,57	0,57	0,58
	Test data	0,53	0,54	0,58	0,53	0,54	0,578
	Ratio	0,9168	0,9312	0,9975	0,9182	0,9329	1,0018
NIR (B8)	S2 Predict	0,51	0,51	0,51	0,52	0,52	0,52
	Test data	0,53	0,54	0,58	0,53	0,54	0,58
	Ratio	1,0359	1,0518	1,1236	1,0174	1,0337	1,1105

For each product tested, the calibration ratios are shown in Figure 5-51 and Figure 5-52.

About the methods, the results confirm good agreements between S2A, LS08, S2B over the Lybia 4 CEOS PICS site with radiometric differences within 2-3 %.

It confirms that the method for the comparison with PlanetScope data is reliable.

Figure 5-51: Cross calibration between DOVE and Sentinel 2A.

Figure 5-52: Cross calibration between DOVE and Sentinel 2B.

5.7 Radiometric Calibration / Validation: Absolute calibration of PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 MSI by using RadCalNet

5.7.1 Activity Description Sheet

Radiometric Accuracy Validation
<p><u>Inputs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set of Level 1C S2 / MSI • Set of Level 1 PlanetScope data
<p><u>Description</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was estimated the absolute radiometric calibration accuracy of PlanetScope data. • Radiometric values of PlanetScope / Sentinel 2 MSI were compared with relative calibration results over PICS, reported in the section 5.6. • RadCalNet, La Crau Site station, were used as reference dataset
<p><u>Outputs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absolute calibration ratio for DOVE and Sentinel 2

5.7.2 Introduction

RadCalNet is an initiative of the Working Group on Calibration and Validation of CEOS. The RadCalNet service provides satellite operators with SI-traceable TOA spectrally-resolved reflectances to aid in the post-launch radiometric calibration and validation of optical imaging sensor data. The free and open access service provides a continuously updated archive of TOA reflectances derived over a network of sites, with associated uncertainties, at a 10 nm spectral sampling interval, in the spectral range from 380 nm to 2500 nm and at 30-minute intervals.

5.7.3 Methods and Tools

5.7.3.1 Methods

The method used for this exercise consists of the following stages:

- Extract PlanetScope calibrated measurement recorded over the region of interest defined over the geographic location of the La Crau station. Nominally the region is 60 m x 60 m, different ROI sizes have been considered to test the sensitivity of the methods.
- It was retrieved from the RadCalNet portal the TOA measurements at the date / time of PlanetScope satellite overpass, if required interpolate these measurements to get spectra values at the exact time, convolving the spectral response of the sensor for the concerned channel.

- Transform the PlanetScope TOA measurements into RadCalNet viewing geometry (RadCalNet is provided at Nadir with an Azimuth angle of 0°) – this transformation is based on a BRDF model
 - The coefficients of the model (BRDF weights, f_{iso} , f_{vol} , f_{geo}) are extracted from the MODIS data (MCD43).
 - The two-volume scattering and geometric kernels K_{vol} , K_{geo} are computed for the PlanetScope, RadCalNet geometries: solar / zenith angle and the relative azimuth.
- Compute ratio between BRDF Corrected PlanetScope Mean TOA (over ROI) and RadCalNet TOA.

Because the viewing zenith angle of PlanetScope is relatively small, a large influence of the BRDF in the calibration results is not expected, except for the Near Infrared Band. Furthermore, the method has been applied also for Sentinel-2A data for which the viewing angle is greater.

Note that MODIS data pixel spacing is 500.0 m and therefore largely above the area covered with station (30 m radius). As the area is uniform, as shown in the image below, the BRDF characterisation should remain valid in the context of this validation.

Note also that the viewing geometry of PlanetScope is given at the scene centre. As the RadCalNet station is located in the eastern / western part of the image, as shown below, the viewing geometry has been estimated for this location.

Figure 5-53: PlanetScope Ortho tile, and RadCalNet location in the weastern part of the image.

5.7.3.2 Tools

Tools are mostly in-house based on ad hoc scripts.

5.7.4 Dataset

5.7.4.1 Region of interest

As detailed in RD-14, the top-of-atmosphere reflectance spectra over the La Crau RadCalNet site are representative of a disk of 30 m radius centred on latitude 43.55885 degrees and longitude 4.864472 degrees. The site is shown in the figure below.

Figure 5-54: La Crau station location, (RadCalNet). Background PlanetScope image acquired on 19/01/2019

5.7.4.2 Planet Data

- 2019-01-19T10:05:33.722266+00:00

5.7.4.3 Sentinel-2 Data

- 2019-03-29T10:48:51.950452Z

5.7.4.4 Modis Data

- MCD43A1.A2019088.h18v04.006.2019099171714
- MCD43A1.A2019024.h18v04.006.2019036201050

5.7.5 Calibration results

The calibration results based on in situ RadCalNet data are listed in Table 5-9. The results from the two stages (with and without BRDF correction) are reported. The PlanetScope results are given together with the S2B results. S2B results are added to validate the method. In terms of percentage difference, the final calibration results are as follows:

- 14 % for the BLUE band,
- 21% for the GREEN,
- 17% for RED bands,
- 5% for the NIR bands,

A comparison of results as obtained from the two methods (PICS / RadCalNet) is done as part of the conclusion (see section 6).

Table 5-9: Absolute calibration coefficients with RadCalNet.

Dataset		Dove-Classic, 19 Jan 2019				Sentinel-2B, 29 Mar 2019 (8A)			
Band		Blue	Green	Red	NIR	Blue	Green	Red	NIR
Angular data	theta_s	68.3				42.09			
	phi_s	153.5				158.69			
	theta_v	0.97				8.89			
	phi_v	12.9				273.38			
Mission reflectance	0.146091	0.137203	0.125795	0.232058	0.122149	0.115467	0.128616	0.274147	
RadCalNet reflectance	0.127441	0.113559	0.10773	0.220353	0.120422	0.115552	0.126842	0.278876	
RadCalNet reflectance	1.146342	1.208207	1.167691	1.053116	1.014338	0.999266	1.013988	0.983044	
With BRDF corrections:									
BRDF mission	0.051289	0.086029	0.109045	0.276346	0.058525	0.100325	0.126349	0.284175	
BRDF nadir RadCalNet	0.05138	0.086596	0.109606	0.277614	0.05997	0.1029	0.130154	0.289725	
Ration BRDF (mission / RadCalNet)	0.998244	0.99345	0.994884	0.99543	0.975903	0.097497	0.970765	0.980844	
RadCalNet reflectance (BRDF Corrected)	0.127214	0.112815	0.107179	0.219346	0.117521	0.11266	0.123134	0.273533	
Mission reflectance	0.146091	0.137203	0.125795	0.232058	0.122149	0.115467	0.128616	0.274147	
Gain Input/Ref	1.148381	1.216173	1.173695	1.05795	1.039384	1.02492	1.044525	1.002243	

Figure 5-55: Absolute Calibration results.

6. CONCLUSIONS

6.1 Geometric calibration

The geometric accuracy results are fully in agreement with the product accuracy specifications (10.0 m RMSE).

Table 6-1: Planimetric Accuracy Results (Absolute, in meter unit).

	Piemont (It)	LaCrau (FR)	Wellington (SA)
GCP #sample	14	17	16
meanX (m)	-2,77	-2,89	-2,50
meanY (m)	-1,25	0,00	4,24
stdX (m)	4,23	5,54	2,53
stdY (m)	3,51	6,48	4,23
RMSX (m)	3,04	2,89	4,92
RMSY (m)	3,72	6,48	5,99
RMS (m)	4,81	7,09	7,75
ce90 (m)	8,58	11,65	9,76

By investigating the internal geometry of the Ortho Tile imagery on both the La Crau and Wellington datasets, severe distortions have been observed. These geometric distortions are residual errors from the geometric adjustment between the consecutive Ortho scenes (frame). Comparing two different images observed at two different dates, the terrain relief is causing geometric distortions, meaning that each image is not free from non-systematic distortions as it might be expected from a remote sensing image after Ortho processing has been applied.

The interband registration accuracy is within expectations for B, G, R image bands. There are however strong deviations for the NIR, B band pair. The error budget of the method is generally good, with values up to 0.25 pixels.

6.2 Radiometric assessment

The radiometric calibration of DOVE missions has been validated using two independent approaches:

- Inter comparison with reference measurements (S2A / S2B / LS08 missions) recorded over Pseudo Invariant Calibration Site (Libya 4),
- Inter comparison with reference measurements from the RadCalNet, Radiometric Calibration Network (La Crau site).

The radiometric calibration is a key aspect of the mission. For DOVE, two important aspects have been analysed, the inter calibration accuracy with reference measurements and the multi temporal calibration stability.

The comparison between DOVE and S2A / S2B / LS08 sensor is not straightforward because the spectral response of DOVE is specific. As shown in the Figure 6-56 matching between spectral responses exists only for the DOVE BLUE and the DOVE NIR bands. It means that with the current method, the cross calibration results over desert for the BLUE and NIR band is not fully relevant. However, the radiometric calibration stability results can be considered.

The calibration of the DOVE GREEN and the DOVE RED is addressed with the RadCalNet methods.

Within the constellation, the inter calibration is correct. Indeed, the comparison of the two calibration ratios for the two different dates shows a good temporal stability. More dates should have been considered to confirm this.

The two methods agree for the PS2 BLUE and PS2 NIR bands. For the two other bands, RadCalNet results are retained. Finally, the following percentage difference per PS2 band can be issued:

- 14 % for the BLUE band,
- 21% for the GREEN,
- 17% for RED bands,
- 5% for the NIR bands,

Figure 6-56: Relative spectral response difference, PS2 / S2 MSI.

APPENDIX A PLANETSCOPE (DOVE) MISSION

Since the launch of the demonstration satellites “DOVE 1” and “DOVE 2” in April 2013, Planet has successfully deployed more than one hundred CubeSats to form the PlanetScope (DOVE) constellation. Ensuring close flight frequency, and operating a continuous image collection, the constellation achieves full global coverage every day with 3-5 m resolution optical data.

As of 2017, Planet has launched three versions of its optical system, PlanetScope 0 (**PS0**), PlanetScope 1 (**PS1**), and PlanetScope 2 (**PS2**), further evolution of the sensor can be found on www.planet.com. The latest sensor PS2 features a five-element optical system that provides a wider field of view and superior image quality. This optical system is paired with a 29MP CCD detector.

Satellites are deployed into two types of orbit: operative satellites are position on sun synchronous orbits at 98 degrees inclination or higher at approximately 475 km and testing satellites are positioned on the International Space Station (**ISS**) orbits at a 52 degrees inclination at approximately 420 km altitude.

The mission continuity of the PlanetScope constellation is maintained by replenishing/upgrading satellites, so there is the need to analyse documentation regarding the constellation evolution and configuration control. The PlanetScope CubeSats were launched in different “Flocks”. A full list of launch dates and satellites put in orbit is available at: https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/flock-1.htm.

Instrument Design and Image Quality

The PlanetScope instrument design is complex and requires a lot of on-board and on-ground processing to get usable images, as shown in Figure A-57, where the “Bayer Mask” concept is explained.

4-tap Bayer-Masked CCD Array

Figure A-57: DOVE instrument design & Bayer Masked CCD Array principles

The sensor specific processing includes the demosaicing of an image from the Bayer CCD, and this would also apply to any TDI sensor (notably with Pan sharpening). The issue is that this processing introduces several artefacts in the image, as discussed in [RD-13]. These artefacts are then filtered out during ground processing and it impacts the overall SNR / MTF results.

Radiometric Calibration

The on orbit radiometric calibration results, as reported in the JACIE 2017 conference, are shown in Figure A-58. The absolute accuracy is not within 5% for all bands and the precision (variability of results) is low; in particular in the blue and green bands that are affected by the Rayleigh scattering.

	Abs Accuracy	Precision (1-sigma)
Blue	-5.15	4.33
Green	-1.08	4.61
Red	0.0005	3.48
NIR	-3.50	3.76

13 Collects from 7 Satellites
between July and October 2016

Figure A-58: Calibration accuracy of DOVE.

In addition, the method is based on a cross comparison with RapidEye data for which there is a mismatch between RSR definition. Later feedback from Planet confirmed that they do compensate RSR differences by using Spectral Band Adjustment Factors (**SBAFs**) for the appropriate terrain cover reference spectra for each PICS site when doing the cross-calibration or cross-validation of their payloads against other satellites.

APPENDIX B LIST OF PLANETSCOPE PRODUCTS USED

ID	Flock	Launch Date	Site	Product_Type	Product_Identifier
1	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	La_Crau	PS2 Ortho_Tile	2037910_3159121 _2019-01-19_1010
	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	La_Crau	PS2 Ortho_Tile	2037910_3159221 _2019-01-19_1010
2	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	La_Crau	PS2 Ortho_Tile	2071879_3159120 _2019-01-30_101b
	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	La_Crau	PS2 Ortho_Tile	2071879_3159121 _2019-01-30_101b
3	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Libya_4	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1713589_3452224 _2018-09-21_1011
4	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Libya_4	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1709099_3452224 _2018-09-19_of22
5	Flock-2k	14/07/2017	Piemont	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1981806_3259709 _2018-12-31_1053
	Flock-2k	14/07/2017	Piemont	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1981806_3259609 _2018-12-31_1053
	Flock-2k	14/07/2017	Piemont	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1981806_3259710 _2018-12-31_1053
6	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Adana	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1876831_3656023 _2018-11-25_1044
	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Adana	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1876831_3656123 _2018-11-25_1044
7	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Adana	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1877011_3656023 _2018-11-25_1034
8	Flock-3p	15/02/2017	Wellington	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1973356_3423606 _2018-12-28_1042
9	Flock-2k	14/07/2017	Wellington	PS2 Ortho_Tile	1891367_3423606 _2018-11-30_104b

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